

TENSILE FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF GFRP FOR SHIP STRUCTURE AFTER LONG TERM OPERATION

Sadayoshi Chiaki ¹, Akio Sakurai ¹, Satoshi Tsusima ¹,
Masao Ono ¹, Norio Fukiage ²

¹ Osaka Branch, Ship Research Institute, Ministry of Transport
Amanogahara 3-5-10, Katano, Osaka 576-0034, Japan

² IMETEC FUKIAGE, Kisaiti 2-17-24, Katano, Osaka 576-0034, Japan

Key Words : Fatigue strength, Secant modulus, GFRP

INTRODUCTION

The ordinary small boats in Japan are made of GFRP plates, which have the MR laminating pattern, where M is chopped strand mat and R denotes roving cloth. The changes of material property caused by a long term operations and a passage of time significantly make effects to the life times of structures. Many researchers has been studying the effect over wide fields.

The authors performed a series of static and fatigue tests of MR plates (1). The changes of fatigue characteristicity of MR plate after long term operation were reported focused on the tendencies of secant modulus and S-N diagram. The applicability of a so-called two parameter model, which is a fatigue life prediction model, to virgin MR plate was validated for tensile-tensile loading case. In this paper, comparisons of the fatigue characteristicities between virgin and used MR plates are discussed based on the additional tensile-tensile fatigue test's results.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

The specimens were rectangle in shape, and were cut out from both MR laminated virgin plate and a bottom plate of a GFRP boat used over 17 years. The cutting directions were longitudinal and transverse to the boat's length. The average dimensions and lay up patterns of specimens are shown in Table 1, where M', M are 450, 600 [g/m²] chopped strand mat and R', R are 580, 810 [g/ m²] roving cloth, respectively. The series names, UPO3, TLBT3, TLBL5, in table 1 means **U**nsaturated **P**OLyester number **3**, **T**ensile **L**eft **B**ottom **T**ransverse **3**, **T**ensile **L**eft **B**ottom **L**ongitudinal **5** for short. The UPO3 series from virgin plate were the same one that in the previous report at ICCM12 (1), which has nearly the same dimensions and lay up as the used series but, V_f, fiber volume fraction.

Table 1: Dimensions and lay up of specimens for fatigue test

Series Names	Lay up	Thickness [mm]	Breadth [mm]	Length [mm]	V _f [%]
UPO3	(M'+R') × 3 + M'	9.23	19.8	249.5	35.2
TLBT3	(M'+R) × 4 + M	9.81	20.0	249.6	24.1
TLBL5	(M'+R) × 4 + M	9.36	19.8	249.7	25.9

TEST PROCEDURE

The fatigue tests were performed by a servomotor controlled testing machine with 98 [GPa] on the capacity. The both ends of each specimen were chucked as 150 [mm] in length and

subjected to sinusoidal cyclic loads under the conditions of 5 [Hz] in frequency and 0 for stress ratio as tensile-tensile. The maximum and minimum values of load and displacement were measured during the tests at every setting number of cycles. All the specimens for the analysis broke at between the chucks and the other irregularly broken ones are included in the tables and figures for comparison.

TEST RESULTS

The fatigue test results are shown in Fig.1 for TUPO3 and Fig.2 for TLBT3, respectively.

Fig.1 The S-N plot for TUPO3 series

Fig.2 The S-N plot for TLBT3 series

The solid lines in the figures show the best fitting results by the least square method. The fatigue sensitivity (2), 'B' is defined by

$$S_{\max} / S_0 = A - B \log N \quad (1)$$

where S_{\max} and S_0 denote the maximum stress amplitude and the average tensile static strength, respectively. The values of B are 0.14 for TUPO3 and 0.068 for TLBT3. It seems that the fatigue sensitivity will decrease for tensile loading after long term operation. The transition

Fig.3 Transition curve of secant modulus for TUPO3 series

Fig.4 Transition curve of secant modulus for TLBT3 series

curves of secant modulus for each series are shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. It is observed that the figures of both series are similarly the same, which implies the fatigue damage accumulating process does not change after long term substantial loading.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the fatigue sensitivity and the transition curves of secant modulus for virgin and used MR plates were compared based on the fatigue test's results. The following notable tendencies were observed.

1. The values of fatigue sensitivity, B , were 0.14 for the virgin series and 0.068 for the used one.
2. The transition curves of secant modulus for each series were similarly the same.

REFERENCE

1. S.Chiaki and A.Sakurai, "On the transitions of secant modulus of GFRP laminates for ship structure during fatigue test", the proceedings of 12th ICCM, 1999, pap1287.
2. Reifsnider, K.L., "Fatigue of Composite Materials", Comp. Mater. Series, p.231(1991), Elsevier.